

**RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY OF BASIC EDUCATION TEACHERS ACROSS
KEY STAGES IN CATANAUAN DISTRICT II, DIVISION OF QUEZON:
BASIS FOR A DISTRICT RESEARCH
ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM**

Sherlyn P. Abellanida, MA and Edelwina M. Blase, PhD

*Master of Arts in Education, Educational Management Program
Marinduque State College extended programs to Eastern Quezon College Inc,
Gumaca, Quezon, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11311508>

ABSTRACT

The study aims to assess the research productivity of basic education teachers across key stages in Catanauan District II. Descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized to analyze the key stages and research productivity of the respondents, frequency counts and percentage were computed. The study reveals the largest group across various key stages is in Kinder to Grades 1-3. Where for the production, 64 research works completed categorized as Action Research while 45 papers are Basic Research, 76 of the respondents have not completed any type of research. Majority of the teachers who have research works followed the teaching and learning theme with 89.01 while child protection and governance were the lowest among the themes. On the number of published works, majority of the teachers who have presented and published their research study were from key stages 1 and 2 where in the school level as well as in the level of adoption. The study shows using the ANOVA that there is a significant difference on the level of research productivity among teacher- respondents based on their key stage assignment. The highly encountered challenges encountered are insufficient time to conduct research and too many ancillaries work aside from teaching while the top strategies that are sometimes employed are listening to the experiences of colleagues who are highly engaged in research. The study suggests that district and school research committee may encourage and support the conduct of research by developing programs or initiatives that facilitate and guide teachers in conducting action research.

Keywords: *research productivity, production, dissemination, utilization, key stages*

INTRODUCTION

Research is an essential area not just in the field of education but in other fields as well. It purifies people's life and their daily activities. It is an effort to learn more and is concerned with quality improvement. It demonstrates how to offer solutions to issues thoroughly and scientifically. Learning new information across all fields is a systematic process. In the educational setting, research plays a significant role in improving processes, including the overall development of pedagogy, learning programs, and policy-making. Further, the educational research provides solutions to different problems in pedagogy while improving teaching and learning practices. Therefore, it is an essential skill and practice that must be consistently performed by each person in educational institutions, including teachers, school managers, and other stakeholders.

The Department of Education (DepEd) urges school administrators to intensify research productivity by improving the research practice in their respective schools. This move is particularly evident in the DepEd Order no. 39 s. 2016, also known as Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda. The order guides DepEd and its stakeholders in the conduct of education research and in the utilization of research results to inform the department's planning, policy, and program development aligned with its vision, mission, and core values.

DepEd encourages teachers' engagement in research through the DepEd Order No. 39 s. 2016 or the Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda. The call to increase research engagement was cascaded to schools, urging educators to research various themes that are essential in improving the entire educational system. Thus, some educators conducted research to study the issues and challenges affecting the effective delivery of education in the country. The move hopes for higher engagement in research among educators and for all research results and outputs to be adequately disseminated and utilized. The DepEd Region IV-A Calabarzon responded to this call to increase the research productivity of the region following the DepEd Research Management Guidelines as stipulated in DepEd Order no 16 s. 2017. Based on the Regional Memorandum no. 714 s. In 2018, roughly 1000 researchers from the region were presented at the 2018 Conference of Basic Education Researchers Southeast Asia through oral presentation, poster presentation, interactive poster presentation, and pecha kucha. This memorandum indicates that some educators in DepEd Calabarzon are engaged in research.

The statement was proven by the study of Cabangangan (2019), where she revealed that the research culture in the secondary schools in DepEd Region IV-A Calabarzon is evident. Specifically, strong evidence of research culture emerges in the research policies implemented, while other components such as school working conditions, research benefits and incentives, collaboration, and networking are only evident. However, some dimensions of research culture need to be given focus, especially on the budget for research, infrastructure, and publications. In terms of research practice, DepEd

Calabarzon frequently practices research production, dissemination, utilization, and monitoring and evaluation.

Meanwhile, in DepEd Quezon, some educators are also engaged in research, as evidenced by the series of plenums that were conducted to present the research works conducted on various themes. However, the results of the study made by Cariaga (2018) found that only two out of 10 teachers were able to publish their research works and conducted two or fewer research in the last five years. More monitoring and evaluation of how the research results are utilized in schools needs to be done. Moreover, problems occur in the production, dissemination, and utilization of research results. Not all schools are able to produce research works, be it primary or action research, since only a few schools participate in research activities in the division. Even if DepEd's mandate is explicitly stated, the production of research still needs to grow. Cariaga (2018), stated that fewer teachers in public schools are genuinely engaged in research because they are loaded with teaching and ancillary works. Another problem identified is that most research works done at the school level only sit idly on the shelves, failing to share the findings and results of the research.

According to the district research committee (personal communication, December 2022) in Catanauan District II, only 25 research works were reported in the district research data in the past five years, and most of these research studies are conducted by the same teacher-researchers. Only seven papers were presented in the district, division, and international conferences despite the efforts to provide regular research training to teachers. This report indicates a low research productivity among teachers in the district. However, a detailed report on the research dimensions needs to be provided. Given this scenario, this study was conducted to determine the status of research productivity of basic education teachers across key stages in the district and identify the challenges that constrain them in engaging in research activities to propose a program that will be essential in increasing the research productivity in the district based on the result of the study.

Research Questions

This study assessed the research productivity of basic education teachers across key stages in Catanauan District II, which served as the basis for a district research enhancement program. Specifically, it answered the following research questions:

1. What is the key stage assignment of the teachers with and without research?
2. What is the status of research productivity of the basic education teachers across key stages in terms of:
 - 2.1 Production
 - 2.1.1 Number of research works produced per type of research;
 - 2.1.2 Number of research works produced per theme of research
 - 2.2 Dissemination
 - 2.2.1 Number of research works presented per level of research conference;

2.2.2 Number of published research works per level of publication

2.3 Utilization

2.3.1 Number of research works adopted per level of adoption

3. Is there a significant difference in the research productivity of the teachers when grouped according to Key Stage?
4. What are the challenges encountered by the basic education teachers that affect their research productivity?
5. What are the coping strategies utilized by the basic education teachers to address the challenges encountered?
6. What research enhancement program could be introduced by the researcher based from the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher utilized descriptive research design to assess the status of teachers' productivity, the challenges affecting their research productivity, and their coping strategies to address the challenges. The descriptive research design accurately and systematically describes, observes, or validates aspects of groups collected through quantifiable information, like the relationship among variables in their natural state (Siedlecki, 2020). This is considered the most suitable design to achieve the objectives of the study since it describes the status of research productivity of the teachers in four key stages, such as elementary from kindergarten to grade 3 then grade 4-6, Junior High School, and Senior High School, and the challenges encountered and effects of their optimal research productivity.

This study was conducted in the province of Quezon located in Calabarzon region in Luzon. Specifically, the study covered the fifteen (15) elementary and five (5) secondary schools in the municipality of Catanauan II district, a coastal municipality in the province of Quezon. The locale was selected due to a reported low productivity in research among elementary and secondary teachers in the last five (5) years. The study covered the elementary and secondary teachers including Junior and Senior High School in Catanauan II district with 292 population. The teachers were selected as the respondents since they have a significant role in conducting research that are predominantly evident from the DepEd Order No. 39 S. 2016 which intends to intensify research productivity among teachers. The researcher utilized random sampling technique where every member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. A total of 169 teachers across four key stages were selected randomly to participate in the study using the Slovin's formula with 0.05 margin of error.

The first part of the instrument is the key stage assignment of the respondents, where it has four (4) key stages. The second part of the instrument is the assessment of the status of research productivity of teachers in terms of research production, dissemination, and

utilization. The third part of the instrument, identified the challenges that constrain in the teacher's research productivity and the last part was the coping strategies utilized to address the challenges encountered, both consists of 14 statements. The collected quantitative data were subjected to statistical computations. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were utilized. To analyze the profile and research productivity of the respondents, frequency counts and percentage were computed. Meanwhile, the Likert items for the challenges encountered and coping strategies, frequency of responses and mean were calculated with corresponding descriptive interpretation. Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) as used to test the significant difference of the research productivity of the respondents when grouped according to key stages.

RESULTS

Part I. Key Stage Assignment of the Respondents

Key Stages	Frequency	With Research	Without Research	Percentage
K to Grade 3	72	42	30	42.61
Grade 4-6	57	33	24	33.72
Grade 7-10	29	14	15	17.16
Grade 11-12	11	4	7	6.51
Total	169	93	76	100.00

Part II. Status of Research Productivity

2.1 Production

Table 2.1.1 *Number of Research Produced per Type of research.*

Type of Research	Frequency	KS1	KS2	KS3	KS4	Percentage
Action Research	64	28	19	12	5	58.71
Basic Research	45	18	18	6	3	41.29
Total	109	46	37	18	8	100.00

Table 2.1.2 *Number of Research works produced per themes of research*

Themes	Frequency	KS1	KS2	KS3	KS4	Percentage
Teaching and Learning	97	45	35	13	4	89.01
Child Protection	3	1	1	1	0	1.83

Human Resource Development Governance	6	0	0	3	3	7.33
	3	0	1	1	1	1.83
Total	109	46	37	18	8	100.00

2.2 Dissemination

Table 2.2.1 Number of Research works presented per level of research conference

Level	Frequency	KS1	KS2	KS3	KS4	Percentage
International	3	1	2	0	0	2.75
National	2	0	1	1	0	1.84
Division	19	8	4	4	3	17.43
District	30	14	12	2	2	27.52
School Based	55	23	18	11	3	50.46
Total	109	46	37	18	8	100.00

Table 2.2.2 Number of Research works produced per nature of publication level

Level	Frequency	KS1	KS2	KS3	KS4	Percentage
International	6	2	2	1	1	7.79
National	1	0	0	1	0	1.30
Division	4	1	1	0	2	5.19
District	18	6	4	5	3	23.38
School Based	48	23	14	9	2	62.34
Total	77	32	21	16	8	100.00

2.3 Utilization

Table 2.3.1 Number of Research works adopted per level of adoption

Level	Frequency	KS1	KS2	KS3	KS4	Percentage
International	1	0	1	0	0	1.40
National	1	0	1	0	0	1.40
Division	2	1	0	0	1	2.80
District	9	4	2	2	1	12.70
School Based	58	28	15	9	6	81.70
Total	71	33	19	11	8	100.00

Part III. Significant difference on the research productivity of the teachers when grouped according to Key Stage

Table 3 Statistical table showing the significant difference on the research productivity of teacher respondent when grouper according to key stage

Variables	P-value	Verbal Interpretation	Decision
Key Stage vs Research Productivity	.001	Significant	Reject Ho

Part IV. Challenges affecting the Research Productivity of Teachers

Table 4 Challenges encountered by the teacher respondents that they considered affect their research productivity

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VD
	4	3	2	1		
1. Limited exposure to and awareness of research writing	42	74	38	15	2.84	ME
2. Negative beliefs towards research.	25	72	45	27	2.56	ME
3. Low level of willingness to make use of research results to improve teaching practices.	29	74	49	17	2.68	ME
4. Limited opportunities provided to teacher-researchers to attend research trainings.	42	69	43	15	2.82	ME
5. Insufficient funding/budget for research.	75	58	24	12	3.16	ME
6. Lack of researchers' authority to initiate dissemination and utilization of research findings and outputs in the school.	40	71	43	15	2.80	ME
7. Insufficient time of teachers to conduct research study.	97	43	17	12	3.33	HE
8. Low level of communication skills of teacher-researchers in presenting research works.	25	80	43	21	2.65	ME
9. Limited opportunities to attend research conferences.	44	72	40	13	2.87	ME
10. Limited administrative support and encouragement in research activities received by teacher-researchers from school leaders.	37	60	48	24	2.65	ME

11. Lack of rewards and incentives for teacher-researchers.	36	72	41	20	2.73	ME
12. Insufficient research resources in the school.	39	79	34	17	2.82	ME
13. Limited support provided by the school research committee to provide technical assistance to teacher-researchers.	36	60	46	27	2.62	ME
14. Too many ancillary works aside from teaching.	97	41	19	12	3.32	HE
Grand Mean					2.84	ME

Legend

- 1.00 – 1.74 Not Encountered (NE)
- 1.75 – 2.49 Least Encountered (LE)
- 2.50 – 3.24 Moderately Encountered (ME)
- 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Encountered (HE)
- VD - Verbal Description

Part V. Coping Strategies Utilized to Address the Challenges Encountered

Table 5 Coping strategies of the teacher respondents on the challenges encountered

Indicators	Frequency				Mean	VD
	4	3	2	1		
1. I attend to research trainings to broaden my knowledge on research writing.	36	64	52	17	2.70	SP
2. I listen to the experiences of my colleagues who are highly engaged in research to develop my own motivation to do research.	51	73	31	14	2.95	SP
3. I make sure that my research outputs are properly utilized to improve my teaching practices.	36	63	39	31	2.62	SP
4. I finance my own research trainings to develop my research skills.	52	51	33	33	2.72	SP
5. I identify potential research partner who can help me fund my research undertakings.	24	63	44	38	2.43	RP
6. I submit the research results to my school head for the dissemination and utilization of research findings and outputs in the school.	28	55	40	46	2.38	RP
7. I allot specific time for me to complete my research works.	24	60	45	40	2.40	RP

8. I ask for technical assistance from my school head or co-teachers who can help me in presenting my research work.	32	61	43	33	2.54	SP
9. I search for possible research trainings that can help develop my research skills if there are no available trainings in the school.	23	68	48	30	2.50	SP
10. I submit my research proposal to my school head to gain approval and support.	32	55	40	42	2.46	RP
11. I submit my research works to various conferences for improvement and recognition.	22	44	48	55	2.20	RP
12. I spend my personal money to provide the resources needed to complete my research work.	43	53	36	37	2.60	SP
13. I look for other research practitioners who can provide technical assistance in research writing aside from the school research committee.	27	64	39	39	2.47	RP
14. I make sure that my ancillary works do not affect my time to conduct research by managing my time effectively.	24	68	41	36	2.47	RP
Grand Mean					2.53	SP

Legend

- 1.00 – 1.74 Not Practiced (NP)
- 1.75 – 2.49 Rarely Practiced (RP)
- 2.50 – 3.24 Sometimes Practiced (SP)
- 3.25 – 4.00 Always Practiced (AP)
- VD - Verbal Description

Proposed Enhancement Program

I. RATIONALE

Research plays a crucial role in the success of an organization specially in schools. This is because continuous improvement, evidence-based decision-making, and the delivery of high-quality education all depend on educational research. It guarantees that the educational system continues to be dynamic, efficient, and accountable while assisting schools in adapting to shifting demands and obstacles. Thus, it is important for schools to develop a strong research culture by increasing the research productivity of its teachers.

The results of the study disclosed that teachers have low research productivity since majority have not produced, presented, or published their research works. The low production, limited dissemination and utilization of results and outputs can be attributed

to several factors or challenges that teacher encounter such as insufficient time to conduct research, too many ancillaries work aside from teaching, insufficient budget/funding for research, and limited opportunities to attend research conferences and research trainings.

The Department of Education, together with the Department of Interior and Local Government and Department of Budget and Management implemented the Circular No.2, s.2020 to widen the use of the Special Education Fund to support the Educational Research. Other than the research subject areas funded in the DepEd budget, subject to the prevailing policies and guidelines of the DepEd.

The Teachers' Research Productivity Enhancement (TRPE) Initiative is to help teachers meet the need for more productive research. The curriculum is based on results that emphasize the varied but underutilized methods of research adoption and dissemination, as well as the significant emphasis on action research and teaching and learning themes. Furthermore, the program acknowledges that research productivity varies significantly between Key Stages and attempts to mitigate the difficulties by implementing various supportive measures.

II. OBJECTIVES

The program seeks to empower teachers and nurture a culture of research excellence, ultimately contributing to improved educational practices and student outcomes. It aims to harness the potential of educators to positively impact the educational landscape through research and innovation. Specifically, it aims to:

1. Encourage and support teachers to actively engage in research activities.
2. Facilitate the dissemination and publication of research findings.
3. Promote the adoption of research outputs in various educational contexts.
4. Address challenges affecting research productivity by providing solutions and resources.
5. Strengthen teachers' coping strategies to overcome barriers and enhance research skills.

III. SCOPE

The program will target teachers across the four Key Stages in the educational system. It will encompass multiple aspects of research, including conducting research, disseminating findings, publishing, and adopting research outputs. The program's activities will be implemented at the school level.

IV. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

This program anticipates the following outcomes:

1. Increased engagement in research activities by teachers.

2. Enhanced research dissemination and publication rates, particularly at school and district levels.
3. Greater adoption of research outputs within the educational community.
4. Mitigation of challenges affecting research productivity, resulting in a more conducive research environment.
5. Improved coping strategies and research skills among teachers, leading to more effective and impactful research outcomes.
- 6.

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Activities and Strategies	Persons Involved	Timeframe	Resources/Fund
Research Production	Conduct workshops that guide teachers through the process of conducting action research in various research themes.	Research Incubation Workshops Session 1: Identifying Research Problems (exploring other research themes) Session 2: Writing the Literature Review Session 3: Designing the Research Methodology Session 4: Data Analysis and Interpretation	School Research Committee Teachers School Head	August to October	10% /session MOOE
		Peer-to-peer knowledge sharing sessions.	Teacher-researchers and mentors	Year round	None Required

		Mentoring novice researchers LAC Session: Time Management Strategies of Effective Teacher-Researchers	School Research Committee Teachers School Head	TBA based on school LAC Session schedules	10% from the MOOE
	Promote collaboration among educators to conduct joint research projects.	Formation of research groups to address common educational challenges.	Teacher-Researchers School Research Committee	During the title proposal	none required
	Allocate resources for research projects that align with school priorities and in the school Annual Implementation Plan.	Presentation and Approval of Research Proposals for Funding	School Head Bookkeeper School Research Committee	To be announced	10% /per research (MOOE)
	Implement a system to recognize and reward teachers for their research efforts and achievements.	“Gawad Pagkilala sa Saliksik” – Annual Recognition of Research Works	School Research Committee School Head	May	10,000 from SEF
Research Dissemination	Provide resources and training to help teachers publish their	Training on Publication and Dissemination Support	School Research Committee Teachers	April	10% from the MOOE

	research findings.				
	Organize school-level research presentations and encourage participation in district-level conferences.	School Research Forum	School Research Committee Teachers School Head	June	5,000 from SEF
	Establish a peer-review process for research papers and presentations.	Guidelines on Peer Review Peer Review of Submitted Research Works	Teacher-Researchers Research Mentors	July	none required
	Provide guidance on how to publish research findings in journals, newsletters, or local school publications.	LAC Sessions on the FAQs about research publication	School Research Committee Teachers	June	10% from the MOOE
Research Utilization	Establish a platform for sharing research findings within and across schools.	Recognition of successful research adoption stories	Teachers School Research Committee	During the Gawad Pagkilala sa Saliksik	to be included in the Gawad Pagkilala Budget
	Create research adoption frameworks	Development of guidelines and frameworks for adopting research findings in teaching practices.	School Research Committee School Heads	August	none required.

		<p>Provision of templates for educators to implement research-based strategies in the classroom.</p> <p>LAC session on translating research into actionable strategies for improving teaching.</p> <p>Recognition and rewarding teachers who successfully implement research-based practices in their classrooms.</p>	<p>School Research Committee Teachers</p> <p>School Research Committee Teachers</p>	<p>TBA based on school LAC Session schedules</p> <p>to be included in the Gawad Pagkilala fund</p>	<p>10% from the MOOE</p>
	<p>Conduct evaluation and impact assessment of adopted research works.</p>	<p>Establishment of feedback mechanisms where teachers can report on the outcomes of research adoption.</p> <p>Submission of feedback report after the evaluation</p>	<p>School Research Committee School Head</p>	<p>August</p>	<p>none required</p>

DISCUSSION

The information the researcher obtained to address the issues raised in the Statement of the Problem (SOP) is presented in this chapter. This information was gathered using the study's quantitative instruments.

Part I. Key Stage Assignment of the Respondents

Table 1 highlights the distribution of teachers across various Key Stages. The largest group is in the Kindergarten to Grades 1-3, with 42 teachers who have research, followed by the teachers in the Grade 4-6, with 33 teachers who have research. The junior and senior high school levels both being the smallest groups in the dataset with a combined 18 teachers with research conducted. These Key Stages represent different levels of education, and the distribution provides insight into the composition of teachers in the different key stages with number of teachers who have conducted and without research. This implies a low engagement of teachers in research since out of 169 respondents, only 93 teachers who have research works conducted.

Part II. Status of Research Productivity

2.1 Production

Number of produced research works per type of research are listed in Table 2.1.1, with a breakdown of research frequency and proportion. According to the total number of research papers generated, the frequencies and percentages show the proportion of each category and the number of researches produced per key stages. As presented above, majority of the respondents, 64 or 58.71% has completed action research while 45 or 41.29% has conducted basic research. Based on the results, action research is the most prevalent type of research among teachers particularly from the key stages 1 and 2, accounting for over half of the research works. This indicates that a significant portion of teachers engage in research that focuses on addressing specific classroom challenges and improving teaching practices. This can be attributed to the fact that DepEd Order 16. S. 2017 encourages teachers to conduct research to solve their classroom problems and improve their teaching practices.

Table 2.1.2

Displays the number of research works produced per themes, along with their respective frequencies and percentages. The table showcases the distribution of research works produced per key stages and categorized by their respective themes. The frequencies and percentages indicate the proportion of each theme relative to the total number of research works produced. Majority of the teachers who have written research works followed the teaching and learning theme because of the mandated DepEd Order no. 16, s. 2017 to guide teachers in managing research initiatives and the results instill fresh materials for instruction and in the classroom. The data underscore the diversity of themes explored by teachers in their research works. The theme of teaching and learning dominates, reflecting the emphasis on improving educational practices and student

outcomes. Additionally, the presence of research in child protection, human resource and development, and governance indicates the broader scope of research interests among teacher-researchers, which can contribute to the development and enhancement of educational practices and policies.

2.2 Dissemination

Table 2.2.1 shows the number of research works presented per level of research conferences attended by the basic education teachers in the district. It can be gleaned from the data that 50.46% or 55 of the teachers have presented research at the school level. Moreover, 30 teacher-researchers have presented in the district and 19 in the division level. Meanwhile, 5 teachers have presented their works in the national and international levels.

The findings show that, there is active participation at all levels from key stages 1 and 2 as from school-based to district-level conferences. Furthermore, the attendance of educators at international conferences implies that a portion of them is involved in disseminating their findings through a wider range of channels. These conferences are essential to the dissemination of research findings and the promotion of educators' professional growth. This suggests a willingness and opportunity to share research findings with their educational community. It is worth noting that a few teacher-researchers have been more prolific in their presentations, with some presenting multiple times in the district.

Table 2.2.2

Shows the number of research works presented per nature research publication. As presented, majority or 62.33% of the research works were published in the school publication (school organ), it shows also that from key stages 1 and 2 got the highest number, while 18 or 23.38% were published in the district publication. Despite the limited number of published research works, the teacher-researchers were able to publish 6 papers in the international publication. The result is supported by Cariaga (2018) that despite the presence of various avenues for research publication, only 2 out of 10 research are published and most research are only presented in the school level in DepEd Quezon. While the number of published research works is limited, it is noteworthy that six papers were successfully published in international publications. This is a positive outcome, as it indicates that some teachers were able to contribute their research findings to a global audience, potentially gaining recognition on an international scale.

3.3 Utilization

Table 3.3.1 shows the number of research works adopted per level of adoption of the research outputs. 58 or 81.70% were able to have their research outputs adopted in the school level since majority of the research works are done for teaching and learning purposes, data shows that key stage 1 got the highest number of adopted research outputs followed by key stage 2 teachers. Mostly, the research outputs adopted in the

school levels are reading programs, according to Tomas, Villaros and Galman, (2021) which can be a good means of such an intervention. In addition, there are 9 research outputs adopted in the district level and 2 in the division level. Meanwhile, 2 research outputs were adopted in the national and international level which provides a positive impact on the utilization of research outputs.

The above data illustrates that while a significant number of teachers did not see their research outputs adopted since from 77 research works published it decreases and only 71 research outputs have been adopted, but a considerable portion did experience adoption at various levels, primarily at the school level. This indicates that teacher-led research can have a positive impact on teaching and learning practices, and in some cases, it can influence education policies at the district, division, and even the national level. These findings highlight the potential benefits of teacher-driven research and the importance of supporting its adoption and utilization in the education system.

Part III. Significant difference on the research productivity of the teachers when grouped according to Key Stage

Table 4 shows that the difference on the level of research productivity among teacher-respondents is statistically significant ($p = .001$). This result illustrates that the research productivity of the teacher respondents varies based on their key stage assignment. The results suggest that when teachers are categorized into different Key Stages, there is a significant difference in how productive they are in terms of research. This could imply that factors related to the specific Key Stage, such as resources available, teaching demands, or institutional support, have an impact on a teacher's ability and motivation to engage in research activities. For instance, teachers in primary education may have different research opportunities and expectations compared to teachers in Junior and Senior High School. These differences in research productivity could have implications for the development and improvement of educational systems and policies to better support research endeavors among teachers in different Key Stages.

Part IV. Challenges affecting the Research Productivity of Teachers

Table 4 amplifies the challenges affecting the research productivity of teachers. It registered an average weighted mean of 2.84 which indicates that the challenges are moderately encountered by the teachers in the district. Accordingly, the highly encountered challenges encountered are insufficient time to conduct research with 3.33 weighted mean and too many ancillary works aside from teaching with a weighted mean of 3.32. Meanwhile, other challenges that are moderately encountered are insufficient budget/funding for research with a weighted mean of 3.15; limited opportunities to attend research conferences with a weighted mean of 2.88 and limited opportunities provided to teacher-researchers to attend research trainings with a weighted mean of 2.83. It is evident that the least challenges encountered by them in conducting research are negative beliefs and limited support provided by the research committee perhaps because they continuously encourage teachers to conduct research through trainings and meetings.

The results indicate that teachers encounter several challenges that significantly impact their research productivity. The most pressing challenges include time constraints and the burden of ancillary tasks, followed closely by financial limitations. It means that teachers often find it difficult to allocate enough time for conducting research due to their regular teaching responsibilities. The heavy workload and time constraints associated with teaching can significantly hinder their research productivity. Moreover, teachers frequently face the burden of ancillary tasks or duties in addition to teaching. These extra responsibilities, which may include administrative work, paperwork, meetings, or other non-teaching duties, can consume a substantial amount of their time and energy, leaving them with limited resources for research.

Part V. Coping Strategies Utilized to Address the Challenges Encountered

Table 5 reveals the coping strategies utilized by the teachers to address the challenges affecting their research productivity. It registered an average weighted mean of 2.53 which indicates that the strategies are sometimes practiced by the teachers.

The top strategies that are sometimes employed are listening to the experiences of colleagues who are highly engaged in research with a weighted mean of 2.95; financing their own research training to develop their research skills with a weighted mean of 2.72; attending to research trainings to broaden their knowledge in research writing with a weighted mean of 2.70; and making sure that research outputs are properly utilized to improve teaching practices with a weighted mean of 2.62. It also shows that 55 teachers did not practice submitting their research works to various conferences for improvement and recognition, it possibly because of too much ancillary works and insufficient budget as stated from their challenges encountered.

The results imply that teachers who engage in research activities find value in learning from their colleagues who are actively involved in research. By sharing their experiences, these more research-oriented colleagues provide insights, guidance, and practical tips that can help others improve their research productivity. Attending research training and personally financing such training are also options but are perceived. These findings highlight the importance of peer learning and time management in improving research productivity among teachers. The results are also supported by Guerrero and Fernandez (2020) that in research, partnerships were highly valued among teachers because the partnerships allowed them to develop pedagogical reflection towards the improvement of their practices and required awareness and recognition of roles and the relationships between practical and theoretical knowledge.

Conclusions

Based on the preceding findings, the following conclusions were derived:

1. The majority of the respondents belong to Key Stage 1 or are described as teachers from Kindergarten to Grades 1 to 3 since the majority of school in Catanauan II is Elementary schools.

2.1 Action research is the dominant type of research produced by teachers focused on the teaching and learning theme, which reflects a strong emphasis on enhancing educational practices and student outcomes. However, a substantial number of teachers need to be more engaging in research activities, suggesting potential areas for further encouragement and support in research endeavors.

2.2 Due to a lack of research to publish or present, most teachers have yet to publish or speak at a conference. Most of the generated research works, however, are presented at the district and school levels and published in the local school newspaper. The results demonstrate how differently the teachers disseminate and publish their study. There is a noticeable presence of research efforts at the district and school levels, even if a large amount of research still needs to be published and shared.

2.3 The majority of the research works are only adopted at the school level. However, a limited number of research works have been adopted since many teachers are not highly engaged in research. The findings underscore the need for greater attention to the utilization of research outputs within the educational community. While many teachers have research to their credit, a significant portion still needs to be addressed, potentially limiting the potential benefits that research could bring to the field. The results also highlight the varying degrees of success in research adoption, with some teachers having their work adopted at different levels, including the national and international stages.

3. There is a significant difference in the level of teachers' research productivity when grouped according to Key Stages. This suggests that when teachers from the key stages are compared, their involvement in research activities, the quantity and quality of their research work, or their overall research productivity could be more consistent. Some Key Stages may have teachers who are more active and productive in research, while others may have fewer research activities or lower research output.

4. The evaluation of challenges affecting the research productivity of teachers in the district reveals a moderate level of encounters with these challenges. The teachers have identified both highly encountered and moderately encountered challenges, shedding light on the factors that may influence their research productivity. The most highly encountered challenges include insufficient time to conduct research and the presence of too many ancillary tasks aside from teaching.

5. The coping mechanisms, which are sporadically put into practice, show how resourceful and committed educators are to conducting successful research. The most often used coping mechanisms include paying for their research training to hone research skills, attending research training to expand knowledge in research writing, hearing from colleagues who are deeply involved in research, and ensuring that research outputs are appropriately utilized to enhance teaching methods. The findings suggest that teachers must take the initiative to address problems that prevent their students from producing high-caliber research. By putting these coping methods into practice, educators expect to overcome resource limitations and enhance their research skills, which will ultimately result in more critical and productive research outputs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings derived from the study and conclusions made, the following recommendations were thus provided:

1. The school research committee may encourage and support the conduct of research in the school by developing programs or initiatives that facilitate and guide teachers in conducting action research. They may also provide mentorship opportunities where experienced teachers can guide and mentor those new to action research.

2. The school head may provide incentives or recognition for teachers who publish their research, even if it is in local school publications. In addition, the school research committee may also organize workshops or training sessions on how to disseminate and publish research findings effectively.

3. The district and school research committee may establish mechanisms for sharing and adopting research findings within schools and districts. They may also encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing among teachers to facilitate the adoption of research outputs by conducting a local research forum to provide an avenue for research works. The committee may also recognize and reward teachers whose research has a positive impact on teaching practices.

4. The teacher-researchers may investigate the factors contributing to differences in research productivity among teachers from different Key Stages. At the same time, the research committee may develop strategies to provide more support and resources to Key Stages with lower research productivity by promoting best practices and successful strategies from Key Stages with high research productivity to others.

5. The school head may reduce the ancillary tasks or non-teaching responsibilities of teachers and allocate time for teachers to conduct research. In addition, they may include research training during INSET and LAC Sessions.

6. The school research committee may feature a teacher-researcher who can share success stories and best practices to inspire and guide teachers in conducting research.

7. The school head may initiate the creation of a culture of research appreciation and support within the school community by recognizing and rewarding teachers who actively engage in research and contribute to the improvement of teaching practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author/s of this study declares that all necessary measures were taken to ensure ethical standards and integrity in the conduct of the research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were made fully aware of the purpose and procedures of the study. Respondents were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. Anonymity of the respondents was strictly maintained, and all data collected were kept confidential and used solely for research purposes. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the duration of the study, and no harm or discomfort was inflicted upon them. The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest that could have influenced the conduct or reporting of the study. Strict measures were taken to avoid plagiarism, and all sources were properly cited. Furthermore, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and results were analyzed objectively to ensure accuracy and validity. The findings of this study were used purely for research purposes and will contribute to the body of knowledge in the field of educational leadership and school climate.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to extend her deepest gratitude to the persons who gave and extended their support for the preparation and journey of this study.

First and Foremost, to Almighty God, who showered the researcher strength and wisdom to overcome all the challenges encountered in her journey. Without his goodness this journey will not be able to continue and accomplished.

To Marinduque State College Chair of Extended Graduate Programs, Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos Jr. and to Eastern Quezon College, Inc. Dean of Graduate Studies, Dr. Melchor B. Espiritu for a wonderful and challenging experiences of the researcher.

Acknowledgement is also given to her personal editor, Dr. Melca D. Cabangangan, to her adviser, Dr. Ma. Edelwina M. Blase, to her statistician, Dr. Noel R. Palomares and to her editor, Dr. Annalyn J. Decena for helping and guiding her throughout her journey in this study.

To her colleagues and friends, for their moral support and help when the researcher asked them about her study. Their support and help gave her additional insights and information. And Of course, to her Family, her husband, Mr. June Angelo M. Abellanida and her son, Zach Mathew P. Abellanida, for the no ending love, support and trust in her, to continue

and make her journey more inspirational even there are times that the researcher wanted to give up but they served as her inspiration to continue all the way.

This study would not be possible without all their love, guidance, and support.

REFERENCES

- Cabanggangan, M. (2019). Research culture and practice in Deped Region IVA Calabarzon: Policy framework plan. An unpublished dissertation. Southern Luzon State University.
- Cariaga, M. (2018). Trends and development in action research among public secondary schools in Quezon Province: Inputs for research capability building program for Secondary School Teachers. Unpublished Dissertation. Manuel S. Enverga Univerisity Foundation, Inc.
- Deped Order No. 16. S.2017. Research management guidelines. deped.gov.ph
- DepEd Oder no. 39 s. 2016. Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda. deped.gov.ph
- Guerrero-Hernández, G.R. and Fernández-Ugalde, R.A. (2020) 'Teachers as researchers: Reflecting on the challenges of research–practice partnerships between school and university in Chile'. *London Review of Education*, 18 (3), 423–38. <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.18.3.07>
- Siedlecki, Sandra. (2020). Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical nurse specialist CNS*. 34. 8-12. 10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493.
- Tomas, M., Villaros, E. and Galman, S. (2021) The Perceived Challenges in Reading of Learners: Basis for School Reading Programs. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 9, 107-122. Doi: 10.4236/jss.2021.95009.
-